

Online Appendix

Foreign Aid and Policy Concessions: Counterterrorism Assistance as Insurance

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General Information

This document serves as the online supplement for the article titled “*Foreign Aid and Policy Concessions: Counterterrorism Assistance as Insurance*”. It contains additional formal proofs and theoretical extensions that were omitted from the main text due to space constraints. The supplemental materials can be accessed via the *Zenodo* repository at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19221530>.

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A.1 Benchmark:

A.1.1 Optimal aid contract with two-sided commitment

The complete Lagrangian for the optimal aid contract with two-sided commitment reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(d_n, c_n, \tau_n) = & \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(d_n) - \tau_n] \\ & + \alpha_n [\tau_n] - \beta_n [c_n + d_n - e_n - \tau_n] + \psi \left[\sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(c_n) - v(e_n)] \right] \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Note that the set of feasible aid contracts as defined by the constraints is non-empty because all the constraints are satisfied under autarky as defined by condition (3). By a standard continuity argument, there exists an optimal aid contract that lies below some upper bound.

The necessary conditions for an optimum are found by differentiating the Lagrangian (10). The Lagrange multipliers for the constraint on aid transfers (1) and the budget constraint (2) in state n are α_n and β_n , respectively, while ψ denotes the multiplier for the recipient's participation constraint (6). The Kuhn–Tucker conditions are:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial d_n} = \pi_n u'(d_n) - \beta_n \leq 0, \quad d_n \geq 0, \quad d_n \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial d_n} = 0, \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial c_n} = \psi \pi_n v'(c_n) - \beta_n \leq 0, \quad c_n \geq 0, \quad c_n \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial c_n} = 0, \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tau_n} = -\pi_n + \alpha_n + \beta_n \leq 0, \quad \tau_n \geq 0, \quad \tau_n \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tau_n} = 0, \quad (13)$$

$$\tau_n \geq 0, \quad \alpha_n \geq 0, \quad \alpha_n \tau_n = 0, \quad (14)$$

$$c_n + d_n - e_n - \tau_n \leq 0, \quad \beta_n \geq 0, \quad \beta_n [c_n + d_n - e_n - \tau_n] = 0, \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(c_n) - v(e_n)] \geq 0, \quad \psi \geq 0, \quad \psi \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(c_n) - v(e_n)] = 0 \quad (16)$$

for all $n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$.

Note that, since $u'(0) = v'(0) = \infty$, expenditure levels d_n and c_n must be strictly positive for all states n in an efficient equilibrium. This implies that first-order conditions (11) and (12) are binding for all states n . The same applies to the budget constraint (15), as it would be inefficient for the recipient not to make use of all available domestic and foreign resources. Under the optimal aid contract, the recipient's participation constraint (16) also always binds,

because the donor skims off the entire surplus from cooperation, leaving the recipient not better off than under autarky.

First, by equating the (binding) first-order conditions (11) and (12), we obtain equilibrium condition I:

$$\frac{u'(d_n)}{v'(c_n)} = \psi. \quad (17)$$

Equilibrium condition I (17) shows that the donor seeks to smooth the ratio of marginal utilities derived from the recipient's spending on defeating a terrorist group d_n and on conventional combat against an (intra- or) international rival c_n across all states n as much as possible until the recipient's participation constraint (16) binds.

Second, first-order conditions (11) and (13) yield equilibrium condition II:

$$\pi_n [u'(d_n) - 1] = 0 \quad \text{if } \tau_n > 0 \quad \text{or} \quad (18a)$$

$$\pi_n [u'(d_n) - 1] < -\alpha_n \quad \text{if } \tau_n = 0. \quad (18b)$$

Equilibrium condition II (18a) demonstrates that if aid is flowing in state n , the donor's marginal gain from the recipient's counterterrorism effort is equal to her marginal cost of providing one unit of aid, which is one, i.e. $u'(d_n) = 1$ if $\tau_n > 0$ ($\alpha_n = 0$). Otherwise, if there are no aid transfers in state n , equilibrium condition II (18b) indicates that the disbursement of aid would cost the donor more than it would benefit her, even if this extra assistance were to be dedicated entirely to counterterrorism purposes, i.e. $u'(d_n) < 1$ if $\tau_n = 0$ ($\alpha_n > 0$).

The following lemmas 1 – 4 characterise the equilibrium under an optimal aid contract with two-sided commitment, as described by Proposition 1. An *optimal aid contract* is non-autarkic and efficient, involving the provision of foreign assistance in at least one income state n .

Lemma 1 *Under the optimal aid contract, expenditures are weakly increasing in the state n , i.e. $d_n \leq d_{n+1}$ and $c_n \leq c_{n+1}$ for all states $n \in \{1, \dots, N-1\}$.*

Intuitively, the recipient's expenditures cannot decline in both policy areas simultaneously when his state capacity is rising, as the government's replenishing fiscal resources must once again be fully reallocated.

Proof: By equilibrium condition I (17), both d_n and c_n must be either constant, increasing, or decreasing in the state n , but cannot move in opposite directions. I next demonstrate that both

must in fact be weakly increasing rather than decreasing in the state n .

Suppose to the contrary that both d_n and c_n are strictly decreasing across some consecutive states n and $n + 1$, that is, $d_n > d_{n+1}$ and $c_n > c_{n+1}$. By the budget constraint (15), we have in states n and $n + 1$

$$c_n + d_n = e_n + \tau_n \quad \text{and} \quad (19a)$$

$$c_{n+1} + d_{n+1} = e_{n+1} + \tau_{n+1}. \quad (19b)$$

Equations (19a) and (19b) imply that $\tau_n > \tau_{n+1}$ because $e_n < e_{n+1}$. By equilibrium condition II (18a and 18b), $\tau_n > \tau_{n+1} \geq 0$ entails that we have in states n and $n + 1$

$$\pi_n [u'(d_n) - 1] = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (20a)$$

$$\pi_{n+1} [u'(d_{n+1}) - 1] \leq 0. \quad (20b)$$

Yet, this yields a contradiction, since $d_n > d_{n+1}$ implies that expression (20a) < (20b). Therefore, it must hold for the optimal aid contract that $d_n \leq d_{n+1}$, and $c_n \leq c_{n+1}$ for all states $n \in \{1, \dots, N - 1\}$. Q.E.D.

Lemma 2 *If $d_n = d_{n+1}$ and $c_n = c_{n+1}$ under the optimal aid contract, then $d_i = d_{n+1}$, $c_i = c_{n+1}$ and $\tau_i > \tau_{i+1} > 0$ for all states $i \leq n$.*

Intuitively, the logic of consumption-smoothing implies that aid inflows should be higher in lower-income phases to stabilise the recipient's spending across income states. Moreover, if expenditures can be completely smoothed across a subset of income states, it is efficient for these to be the lowest ones. The hedge most appreciated by a risk-averse recipient is protection against the most severe adverse income shock. This 'insurance pledge', in turn, provides the donor with the greatest potential leverage in extracting policy concessions.

Proof

Consider states n and $n + 1$, for which the optimal aid contract stipulates that expenditures are completely smoothed. Define $\bar{d} \equiv d_n = d_{n+1}$ and $\bar{c} \equiv c_n = c_{n+1}$. First, I show that $\tau_n > \tau_{n+1} > 0$. By the budget constraint (15), we have in states n and $n + 1$.

$$\bar{c} + \bar{d} = e_n + \tau_n \quad \text{and} \quad (21a)$$

$$\bar{c} + \bar{d} = e_{n+1} + \tau_{n+1}. \quad (21b)$$

Because $e_n < e_{n+1}$, equations (21a) and (21b) imply that $\tau_n > \tau_{n+1}$. Equilibrium condition II (18a) entails that $\tau_{n+1} > 0$ because $\tau_n > 0$ and $d_n = d_{n+1}$.

Second, I demonstrate by process of elimination that $d_i = \bar{d}$ and $c_i = \bar{c}$ for all states $i < n$. By Lemma 1, it must be that $d_i \leq \bar{d}$ for all states $i < n$. Let $d_i < \bar{d}$ for all states $i < n$, and recall that $\tau_n > 0$ in state n . By equilibrium condition II (18a and 18b), we have in states $n-1$ and n

$$\pi_{n-1}[u'(d_{n-1}) - 1] \leq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (22a)$$

$$\pi_n[u'(\bar{d}) - 1] = 0. \quad (22b)$$

However, this yields a contradiction, since $d_{n-1} < \bar{d}$ implies that expression (22a) $>$ (22b). It follows that $d_i = \bar{d}$ for all states $i < n$. Q.E.D.

Lemma 3 *If expenditures cannot be completely smoothed across states n and $n+1$ under the optimal aid contract, i.e. $d_n < d_{n+1}$ and $c_n < c_{n+1}$, then aid payments are zero in state $n+1$, i.e. $\tau_n \geq \tau_{n+1} = 0$.*

Intuitively, complete consumption-smoothing may be infeasible even under the optimal aid contract due to the non-negativity constraint on aid transfers (14). When only partial smoothing is possible, efficiency dictates that assistance be directed towards lower-income states by Lemma 2. Consequently, no aid is allocated to the remaining higher-income states across which expenditures cannot be completely smoothed.

Proof

Consider states n and $n+1$, for which expenditures *cannot* be completely smoothed even under the optimal aid contract. Then, expenditures are strictly increasing in the state n by Lemma 1, i.e. $d_n < d_{n+1}$ and $c_n < c_{n+1}$. By equilibrium condition II (18a and 18b), we have in states n and $n+1$

$$\pi_n[u'(d_n) - 1] \leq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (23a)$$

$$\pi_{n+1}[u'(d_{n+1}) - 1] < 0. \quad (23b)$$

By equilibrium condition II (18b), it follows from inequality (23b) that $\tau_{n+1} = 0$ in state $n + 1$. Q.E.D.

Lemma 4 *Under the optimal aid contract, recipient-preferred expenditures are at least partially smoothed with respect to the recipient's endowment, i.e. $e_1 < c_1 \leq c_N < e_N$. Moreover, the aid payment in the lowest state $n = 1$ is positive and strictly exceeds that in the highest state $n = N$, i.e. $\tau_1 > \tau_N \geq 0$.*

Intuitively, even when complete smoothing of the recipient's preferred expenditures is infeasible, optimality implies that at least partial smoothing relative to the recipient's endowment is achieved, since some intertemporal exchange between the agents remains feasible.

Proof

Suppose to the contrary that $c_1 \leq e_1 < e_N \leq c_N$. By the budget constraint (15), we have in states $n = 1$ and $n = N$

$$c_1 + d_1 = e_1 + \tau_1 \quad \text{and} \quad (24a)$$

$$c_N + d_N = e_N + \tau_N. \quad (24b)$$

Equations (24a) and (24b) then imply that $d_1 \geq \tau_1$ and $d_N \leq \tau_N$. Recall that in any non-autarkic equilibrium, $d_1 \leq d_N$ by Lemma 1 and $\tau_1 > \tau_N$ by Lemma 2 and Lemma 3. Taken together, these (in)equalities entail the following contradiction:

$$d_1 \leq d_N \leq \tau_N < \tau_1 \leq d_1. \quad (25)$$

Therefore, it must be that $e_1 < c_1 \leq c_N < e_N$.

Q.E.D.

A.1.2 Calculation example

To showcase a solution approach to the model, consider the following calculation example: let $e_n \in \{0.1, 0.5\}$, $\pi_n = 0.5$, $u(d_n) = \sqrt{d_n}$ and $v(c_n) = \sqrt{c_n}$ for states $n \in \{1, 2\}$.

Step 1: Determine d_1 .

First, by Proposition 1, $\tau_1 > 0$ in state $n = 1$, implying $\alpha_1 = 0$. By first-order condition (13), we

obtain $\beta_1 = 0.5$. Using first-order condition (11), we get

$$\frac{0.25}{\sqrt{d_1}} = 0.5, \quad (26)$$

which implies $d_1 = 0.25$.

Step 2: Is complete consumption-smoothing feasible?

Second, because the optimal aid contract equalises expenditure levels d_n and c_n as much as possible across all states, we examine whether completely smoothed expenditures across both states $n \in \{1, 2\}$ satisfy all constraints. For this purpose, define $\bar{d} \equiv d_1 = d_2 = 0.25$ using the interim result from *Step 1* as well as $\bar{c} \equiv c_1 = c_2$. Imposing $c_1 = c_2$ on the recipient's participation constraint (16) yields $\bar{c} = 0.26$. We then get $\tau_1 = 0.41$ and $\tau_2 = 0.01$ from the budget constraint (15). Since all constraints are satisfied in this case, expenditures can be completely smoothed across both states under the optimal aid contract.

However, complete consumption-smoothing across all states is not always feasible. To illustrate this case, consider a slightly different endowment set $e_n \in \{0.1, 0.6\}$. Now, the recipient's income stream is more volatile than before. Repeating *Step 1* yields $d_1 = 0.25$ again, whereas *Step 2* gives $\bar{c} = 0.30$, violating the budget constraint (15) in state $n = 2$.

Step 3: Exploit the fact that $\tau_2 = 0$.

In the case where expenditures cannot be completely smoothed across both states, aid transfer $\tau_2 = 0$ by Lemma 3. Using this fact and the budget constraint (15), we can rewrite the recipient's participation constraint (16) and equilibrium condition I (17) as follows:

$$v(e_1) + v(e_2) = v(e_1 + \tau_1 - d_1) + v(e_2 - d_2) \quad \text{and} \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{u'(d_1)}{v'(e_1 + \tau_1 - d_1)} = \frac{u'(d_2)}{v'(e_2 - d_2)}, \quad \text{respectively.} \quad (28)$$

Solving for d_2 and τ_1 , we obtain $d_1 = 0.25 < d_2 = 0.28$, $c_1 = 0.28 < c_2 = 0.32$ and $\tau_1 = 0.43 > \tau_2 = 0$ under the optimal aid contract, implying that expenditure levels cannot be completely equalised across states in this case.

A.2 Optimal aid agreement without commitment

Having characterised the optimal aid contract, I now turn to an implicit aid agreement without any commitment. In each period t , *after* the realisation of state n , the donor's and the recipient's ex post expected continuation payoffs under such an agreement are given by

$$U_n \equiv u(d_n) - \tau_n + \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \delta^t \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(d_n) - \tau_n] \quad (29)$$

$$= u(d_n) - \tau_n + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(d_n) - \tau_n] \quad \text{and}$$

$$V_n \equiv v(c_n) + \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \delta^t \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(c_n)] \quad (30)$$

$$= v(c_n) + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(c_n)], \quad \text{respectively.}$$

An equilibrium of the repeated game is required to be perfect. One such perfect equilibrium is the perpetual repetition of the single-period Nash equilibrium, corresponding to permanent autarky. However, there also exist perfect equilibria that yield each actor higher expected utility than under permanent autarky. Since Pareto-improvements arise from risk-sharing in this economy, at least some degree of consumption-smoothing can be sustained under perfection.

Perfect equilibrium paths can be characterised by adopting trigger strategy punishments. The most severe penalty that can be inflicted on the sovereign agents in the repeated game is reciprocal non-cooperation forever, that is, reversion to permanent autarky. On the one hand, if the donor fails to disburse the equilibrium aid transfer in some state n , the recipient ceases to exert any counterterrorism effort both in the current period and in all future periods. The donor's utility from *deviating* in state n is therefore

$$U_n^D \equiv u(0) + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(0)] = 0. \quad (31)$$

On the other hand, if the recipient deviates from the equilibrium division of national resources in some state n , the donor terminates aid provision permanently from the subsequent period onwards. Because foreign assistance is transferred to the recipient prior to his decision on how to distribute it domestically, the recipient maximises his payoff upon defection by spending all available aid inflows together with his entire endowment on his preferred policy domain,

conventional combat readiness c_n , rather than delivering the agreed-upon policy concessions in the form of counterterrorism effort d_n . Using the budget constraint (2) for $d_n = 0$, the recipient's expected continuation payoff from *deviating* in state n is

$$V_n^D \equiv v(e_n + \tau_n) + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(e_n)]. \quad (32)$$

The possibility that either the donor or the recipient refuses to cooperate with the other imposes the following *no-deviation constraints* on the optimal implicit aid agreement without commitment:

$$U_n \geq U_n^D \quad \text{and} \quad (33)$$

$$V_n \geq V_n^D, \quad \text{respectively, } \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (34)$$

Before deriving the Kuhn–Tucker conditions for an optimum, the following lemma establishes the redundancy of the recipient's participation constraint (6) in the constraint set:

Lemma 5 *The recipient's participation constraint (6) is implied by his no-deviation constraint (34).*

Proof

Using expression (32), and since $\tau_n \geq 0$, we have

$$V_n^D \geq v(e_n) + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(e_n)]. \quad (35)$$

Therefore, the recipient's no-deviation constraint (34) implies that

$$\begin{aligned} V &= \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n V_n \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n V_n^D \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n \left[v(e_n) + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(e_n)] \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(e_n)]. \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

Because expression (36) entails the recipient's participation constraint (6), the lemma is proved. Q.E.D.

A.2.1 One-sided commitment on the donor's side

As a preliminary step towards deriving the optimal implicit aid agreement without any commitment, I analyse the case in which only the donor can commit to a future aid policy. Such an agreement is the solution to the following optimisation problem:

$$\max_{\{d_n, c_n, \tau_n\}} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(d_n) - \tau_n], \quad (37)$$

subject to the non-negativity constraint on aid transfers (1), the budget constraint (2), and the recipient's no-deviation constraint (34) for all $n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. The Lagrange multipliers for the constraints in state n are denoted by α_n , β_n and ρ_n , respectively. The complete Lagrangian for an aid agreement with one-sided commitment on the donor's side reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(d_n, c_n, \tau_n) = & \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(d_n) - \tau_n] \\ & + \alpha_n [\tau_n] - \beta_n [c_n + d_n - e_n - \tau_n] \\ & + \rho_n [v(c_n) - v(e_n + \tau_n) + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(c_n) - v(e_n)]] \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

The Kuhn–Tucker conditions are:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial d_n} = \pi_n u'(d_n) - \beta_n \leq 0, \quad d_n \geq 0, \quad (39)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial c_n} = \rho_n v'(c_n) \left[1 + \frac{\delta \pi_n}{1-\delta} \right] - \beta_n \leq 0, \quad c_n \geq 0, \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tau_n} = -\pi_n + \alpha_n + \beta_n - \rho_n v'(e_n + \tau_n) \leq 0, \quad \tau_n \geq 0, \quad (41)$$

$$\tau_n \geq 0, \quad \alpha_n \geq 0, \quad (42)$$

$$c_n + d_n - e_n - \tau_n \leq 0, \quad \beta_n \geq 0, \quad (43)$$

$$v(c_n) - v(e_n + \tau_n) + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(c_n) - v(e_n)] \geq 0, \quad \rho_n \geq 0, \quad (44)$$

together with the complementary slackness conditions

$$\begin{aligned} d_n \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial d_n} &= c_n \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial c_n} = \tau_n \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tau_n} = \alpha_n[\tau_n] = \beta_n[c_n + d_n - e_n - \tau_n] \\ &= \rho_n \left[v(c_n) - v(e_n + \tau_n) + \frac{\delta}{1 - \delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(c_n) - v(e_n)] \right] = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

for all $n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$.

First, we obtain equilibrium condition I by equating the (binding) first-order conditions (39) and (40):

$$\frac{u'(d_n)}{v'(c_n)} = \rho_n \frac{(1 - \delta) + \delta \pi_n}{(1 - \delta) \pi_n}. \quad (46)$$

Second, first-order conditions (39) and (41) yield equilibrium condition II:

$$\pi_n [u'(d_n) - 1] = \rho_n v'(e_n + \tau_n) \quad \text{if } \tau_n > 0 \quad \text{or} \quad (47a)$$

$$\pi_n [u'(d_n) - 1] < -\alpha_n + \rho_n v'(e_n) \quad \text{if } \tau_n = 0. \quad (47b)$$

The removal of the recipient's commitment restricts the extent of consumption-smoothing achievable under the optimal aid contract, which diminishes the recipient's expected continuation payoff from cooperation at any given date. Since a permanent suspension of aid payments henceforth is rendered a less severe punishment for him than under optimality, the absence of the recipient's commitment forces the donor to settle for a less intense conditionality relative to the optimal aid contract, thereby chipping away at her objective.

The following lemmas 6 – 8 characterise the efficient perfect equilibrium under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment on the donor's side. Let superscripts $(\widehat{\cdot})$ denote variables pertaining to the optimal aid contract with two-sided commitment. Let superscripts $(\widetilde{\cdot})$ signify variables relating to an aid agreement with one-sided commitment.

Lemma 6 *If the recipient's no-deviation constraint (44) under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment binds in some state n in an efficient equilibrium, it will do so in state $n + 1$ as well, i.e. $\rho_{n+1} > 0$ if $\rho_n > 0$.*

Intuitively, the recipient's no-deviation constraint must bind in at least one state for an aid agreement to be efficient. Otherwise, the donor's objective (37) could be raised without dissuading the recipient from cooperating. If the recipient's no-deviation constraint binds in only one state, it must be the highest state $n = N$. This is because the recipient's incentives to

deviate are the greatest during the highest-capacity period, in which not only the size of his state budget but also the amount of policy concessions that he is stipulated to grant are at their largest.

Proof

Suppose to the contrary that there exist some states n and $n + 1$ such that $\rho_n > 0$ and $\rho_{n+1} = 0$. Then, the recipient's no-deviation constraint (44) in states n and $n + 1$ yields

$$v(e_n + \tau_n) - v(c_n) + \frac{\delta}{1 - \delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(e_n) - v(c_n)] = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (48a)$$

$$v(e_{n+1} + \tau_{n+1}) - v(c_{n+1}) + \frac{\delta}{1 - \delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(e_n) - v(c_n)] < 0. \quad (48b)$$

Subtracting inequality (48b) from equality (48a) yields

$$v(e_n + \tau_n) - v(e_{n+1} + \tau_{n+1}) - v(c_n) + v(c_{n+1}) > 0. \quad (49)$$

Using the budget constraint (43), inequality (49) can be rewritten as

$$v(c_n + d_n) - v(c_{n+1} + d_{n+1}) - v(c_n) + v(c_{n+1}) > 0. \quad (50)$$

Inequality (50) implies that the donor's objective can be raised by inducing a higher counter-terrorism effort d_{n+1} at the expense of recipient-preferred spending c_{n+1} in state $n + 1$, until the recipient's no-deviation constraint (48b) binds in that state. This entails that $\rho_{n+1} > 0$ is optimal if $\rho_n > 0$. Q.E.D.

Lemma 7 *If the recipient's no-deviation constraint (44) under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment binds in some state n in an efficient equilibrium, donor-favoured expenditures in this state are strictly smaller than those under the optimal aid contract, i.e. $\tilde{d}_n < \hat{d}_n$ if $\rho_n > 0$.*

Intuitively, the absence of the recipient's commitment complicates the enforcement of compliance, particularly in times of abundance. Relative to the optimal aid contract, sustaining an aid agreement with one-sided commitment therefore requires allowing the recipient to reduce donor-favoured spending first and foremost during high-capacity periods.

Proof

I show that $\tilde{d}_n < \hat{d}_n$ if $\rho_n > 0$ in state n . Two cases are distinguished. First, consider the case in which $\hat{\tau}_n \geq \tilde{\tau}_n > 0$ in some state n . The comparison of equilibrium condition II under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment (47a) and under the optimal aid contract (18a) in state n yields that $\tilde{d}_n < \hat{d}_n$ if $\rho_n > 0$.

Second, consider the case in which $\hat{\tau}_n \geq \tilde{\tau}_n = 0$ in some state n . Without loss of generality, suppose there are only two states, $n \in \{1, N\}$. Since $\tau_1 > 0$ in the lowest state $n = 1$ in any efficient equilibrium, it follows that $\hat{\tau}_N \geq \tilde{\tau}_N = 0$ in state $n = N$. For this state, consider the recipient's binding participation constraint under the optimal aid contract (16) and his binding no-deviation constraint under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment (44), i.e. $\rho_N > 0$:

$$\pi_1[v(\hat{c}_1) - v(e_1)] + \pi_N[v(\hat{c}_N) - v(e_N)] = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (51a)$$

$$\pi_1[v(\tilde{c}_1) - v(e_1)] + \pi_N[v(\tilde{c}_N) - v(e_N)] + \frac{1-\delta}{\delta}(v(\tilde{c}_N) - v(e_N)) = 0. \quad (51b)$$

Note that the recipient's expected continuation surplus over autarky from the next period onwards ($[\delta/(1-\delta)] \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n[v(\tilde{c}_n) - v(e_n)]$) is positive, while his current-period surplus ($v(\tilde{c}_N) - v(e_N)$) is negative. Thus, equations (51a) and (51b) entail that $\tilde{c}_n > \hat{c}_n$ must hold in at least one state, $n = 1$, $n = N$ or both. However, $\tilde{c}_1 > \hat{c}_1$ is not feasible because the degree of consumption-smoothing achievable under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment is strictly lower than that under the optimal aid contract. Consequently, it must be that $\tilde{c}_N > \hat{c}_N$. By the budget constraint (15 and 43), $\tilde{c}_N > \hat{c}_N$ together with $\hat{\tau}_N \geq \tilde{\tau}_N = 0$ implies that $\tilde{d}_N < \hat{d}_N$ in state $n = N$.

Taken together, the two cases establish that $\tilde{d}_n < \hat{d}_n$ whenever $\rho_n > 0$ in state n . Q.E.D.

Lemma 8 *Under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment, a sufficiently low discount factor δ may reduce the critical state n^* as defined in Proposition 1 for the optimal aid contract.*

Intuitively, as the discount factor δ decreases, the recipient's willingness to cooperate becomes more restricted under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment. This may force the donor to limit the provision of security support in comparison to the optimal aid contract so as to prevent the recipient from 'taking the money and running'. Consequently, financial assistance may cease in some state n , even if it had materialised under optimality. Since the critical state n^* is the maximum state that supports the transfer of aid, greater discounting of the future may lead to a lower critical state n^* under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment relative to

the optimal aid contract.

Proof

I prove the lemma by showing that a state n may exist in which $\widehat{\tau}_n > 0$ under the optimal aid contract but $\widetilde{\tau}_n = 0$ under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment if δ is sufficiently small.

Decreasing δ renders the recipient's binding no-deviation constraint (44) under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment more restrictive in some state n . The devaluation of future collaboration may cause equilibrium aid payments in this state to shrink, possibly falling to zero, i.e. $\widehat{\tau}_n > \widetilde{\tau}_n \geq 0$, as otherwise the short-run gain from appropriating the assistance in defection would outweigh the present value of continued cooperation for the recipient. Therefore, the critical state n^* may be lower under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment relative to the optimal aid contract for sufficiently small δ . Q.E.D.

By Lemmas 6 – 8, the following proposition clarifies the key differences between an equilibrium under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment on the donor's side and the optimal aid contract with two-sided commitment:

Proposition 3 *If the discount factor δ is sufficiently low, donor-favoured expenditures d_n in a given state $n = n'$ and in all higher states $n > n'$ under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment are strictly smaller than those under the optimal aid contract, i.e. $\widetilde{d}_n < \widehat{d}_n$ for all states $n \geq n'$. Furthermore, a reduction in the discount factor δ may decrease the critical state n^* under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment as compared to the optimal aid contract.*

A.2.2 No commitment

Finally, I derive the optimal implicit aid agreement without any commitment. Such an agreement is the solution to the following optimisation problem:

$$\max_{\{d_n, c_n, \tau_n\}} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(d_n) - \tau_n], \tag{52}$$

subject to the non-negativity constraint on aid transfers (1), the budget constraint (2), the donor's no-deviation constraint (33), and the recipient's no-deviation constraint (34) for all $n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. The Lagrange multipliers for the constraints in state n are denoted by α_n , β_n , σ_n and ρ_n , respectively. The complete Lagrangian for an aid agreement without commitment

reads:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}(d_n, c_n, \tau_n) &= \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(d_n) - \tau_n] \\
&+ \alpha_n [\tau_n] - \beta_n [c_n + d_n - e_n - \tau_n] \\
&+ \rho_n [v(c_n) - v(e_n + \tau_n)] + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(c_n) - v(e_n)] \\
&+ \sigma_n \left[u(d_n) - \tau_n + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(d_n) - \tau_n] \right] \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{53}$$

The Kuhn–Tucker conditions are:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial d_n} = u'(d_n) \left[\pi_n + \sigma_n \left[1 + \frac{\delta \pi_n}{1-\delta} \right] \right] - \beta_n \leq 0, \quad d_n \geq 0, \tag{54}$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial c_n} = \rho_n \left[v'(c_n) \left[1 + \frac{\delta \pi_n}{1-\delta} \right] \right] - \beta_n \leq 0, \quad c_n \geq 0, \tag{55}$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tau_n} = -\pi_n + \alpha_n + \beta_n - \rho_n v'(e_n + \tau_n) - \sigma_n \left[1 + \frac{\delta \pi_n}{1-\delta} \right] \leq 0, \quad \tau_n \geq 0, \tag{56}$$

$$\tau_n \geq 0, \quad \alpha_n \geq 0, \tag{57}$$

$$c_n + d_n - e_n - \tau_n \leq 0, \quad \beta_n \geq 0, \tag{58}$$

$$v(c_n) - v(e_n + \tau_n) + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(c_n) - v(e_n)] \geq 0, \quad \rho_n \geq 0, \tag{59}$$

$$u(d_n) - \tau_n + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(d_n) - \tau_n] \geq 0 \quad \sigma_n \geq 0, \tag{60}$$

together with the complementary slackness conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
d_n \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial d_n} &= c_n \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial c_n} = \tau_n \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \tau_n} = \alpha_n [\tau_n] = \beta_n [c_n + d_n - e_n - \tau_n] \\
&= \rho_n \left[v(c_n) - v(e_n + \tau_n) + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [v(c_n) - v(e_n)] \right] \\
&= \sigma_n \left[u(d_n) - \tau_n + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(d_n) - \tau_n] \right] = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{61}$$

for all $n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$.

First, we obtain equilibrium condition I by equating the (binding) first-order condi-

tions (54) and (55):

$$\frac{u'(d_n)}{v'(c_n)} = \rho_n \frac{(1 - \delta) + \delta \pi_n}{(1 - \delta)\pi_n + \sigma_n[(1 - \delta) + \delta \pi_n]}. \quad (62)$$

Second, first-order conditions (54) and (56) yield equilibrium condition II:

$$\left(\pi_n + \sigma_n \left[1 + \frac{\delta \pi_n}{1 - \delta} \right] \right) \left[u'(d_n) - 1 \right] = \rho_n v'(e_n + \tau_n) \quad \text{if } \tau_n > 0 \quad \text{or} \quad (63a)$$

$$\left(\pi_n + \sigma_n \left[1 + \frac{\delta \pi_n}{1 - \delta} \right] \right) \left[u'(d_n) - 1 \right] < -\alpha_n + \rho_n v'(e_n) \quad \text{if } \tau_n = 0. \quad (63b)$$

Third, after substituting ρ_n in equations (62) and (63a), we get equilibrium condition III:

$$u'(d_n) \left[1 - \frac{[v'(e_n + \tau_n)]}{[v'(c_n)]} \right] = 1. \quad (64)$$

Equilibrium condition III (64) shows that the donor strives to achieve equality between the marginal benefit of providing foreign assistance on the left-hand side, which is the donor's marginal utility from the recipient's counterterrorism effort weighted by the marginal monetary transfer towards anti-terror purposes for each unit of aid, and the marginal cost of providing security assistance on the right-hand side, which is unity.

As $\delta \rightarrow 1$, an implicit aid agreement without any commitment converges to the optimal aid contract with two-sided commitment, since the set of constraints for the former (57) – (59) approaches that for the latter (14) – (16) for all states n while the donor's no-deviation constraint (60) never binds in the limit.

The following lemmas 9 – 11 characterise the efficient perfect equilibrium under an aid agreement without any commitment, as described by Proposition 2.

Lemma 9 *If the donor's no-deviation constraint (60) under an aid agreement without any commitment binds in some state n in an efficient equilibrium, it will do so in state $n - 1$ as well, i.e. $\sigma_{n-1} > 0$ if $\sigma_n > 0$.*

Intuitively, if the donor's no-deviation constraint binds in only one state, it must be the lowest state $n = 1$. This is because the donor's incentives to deviate are the greatest during the recipient's lowest-capacity phase, in which not only the 'insurance benefits' that the recipient would lay claim to are at their largest but also the policy concessions that the donor is supposed to receive are at their smallest.

Proof

Suppose to the contrary that there exist some states $n-1$ and n such that $\sigma_{n-1} = 0$ and $\sigma_n > 0$. Then, the donor's no-deviation constraint (60) in states $n-1$ and n reads

$$u(d_{n-1}) - \tau_{n-1} + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(d_n) - \tau_n] > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (65a)$$

$$u(d_n) - \tau_n + \frac{\delta}{1-\delta} \sum_{n=1}^N \pi_n [u(d_n) - \tau_n] = 0. \quad (65b)$$

To show that this allocation is inefficient, consider the following deviation: let the donor reallocate part of her aid transfer τ_n in state n to state $n-1$ until her no-deviation constraint (65a) in state $n-1$ binds, while keeping total expected transfers constant. This reallocation does not affect the donor's objective, as her continuation payoff remains unchanged.

Additionally, this alteration does not violate the recipient's no-deviation constraint (59) in either state n , provided recipient-preferred expenditures c_n are adjusted accordingly. Feasible adjustments always exist, since, by the budget constraint (58), $d_n > 0$ implies that $v'(c_n) > v'(e_n + \tau_n)$ for each state n . Therefore, $\sigma_{n-1} > 0$ is optimal if $\sigma_n > 0$. Q.E.D.

Let superscript $\check{(\cdot)}$ denote variables relating to an aid agreement without any commitment. Recall that superscript $\tilde{(\cdot)}$ signifies variables pertaining to an aid agreement with one-sided commitment on the donor's side.

Lemma 10 *If the agents' no-deviation constraints (59 and 60) under an aid agreement without any commitment bind in the lowest state $n = 1$, aid transfers and recipient-preferred expenditures in this state are strictly smaller than those under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment, i.e. $\check{\tau}_1 < \tilde{\tau}_1$ and $\check{c}_1 < \tilde{c}_1$ if $\check{\rho}_1 > 0$ and $\sigma_1 > 0$.*

Intuitively, the removal of the donor's commitment may force her 'insurance payout' to diminish, particularly in times of the recipient's paucity, to maintain the donor's willingness to cooperate in the first place. This further restricts the magnitude of risk-sharing, relative to what is attainable under one-sided commitment, which leads to a reduction in recipient-preferred spending during phases of greatest economic hardship for him.

Proof

Compared with an aid agreement with one-sided commitment, sustaining an aid agreement without any commitment may necessitate a cap on assistance payments in the lowest state

$n = 1$, i.e. $\check{\tau}_1 < \tilde{\tau}_1$. This occurs if, in addition to the no-deviation constraint of the recipient (59), that of the donor (60) also binds, i.e. $\check{\rho}_1 > 0$ and $\sigma_1 > 0$. In this instance, by Lemma 6, no recipient surplus remains to be harnessed to prop up donor-favoured expenditures d_1 in the minimal-capacity state so as to offset the loss of her ability to commit. The resulting curtailment of equilibrium aid flows in the lowest-capacity state necessarily narrows the scope for consumption-smoothing, yielding $\check{c}_1 < \tilde{c}_1$. Q.E.D.

Lemma 11 *If the agents' no-deviation constraints (59 and 60) under an aid agreement without any commitment bind in some state n , aid transfers in the next higher state $n + 1$ may exceed those under an aid agreement with one-sided commitment, i.e. $\check{\tau}_{n+1} > \tilde{\tau}_{n+1}$ if $\check{\rho}_n > 0$ and $\sigma_n > 0$.*

Intuitively, when both no-deviation constraints bind in a given state n , the recipient may require additional remuneration to sustain cooperation under an aid agreement without any commitment as compared to an aid agreement with one-sided commitment. Augmenting aid payments in states n or below is precluded because the donor's readiness to supply assistance in lower-capacity phases is already exhausted by Lemma 9. Consequently, compensation must be provided in states n or above, with the most efficient disbursement of these supplementary 'insurance benefits' occurring in state $n + 1$ rather than in any higher state.

Proof

Without loss of generality, consider the lowest two states, $n = 1$ and $n = 2$. If the recipient's and the donor's no-deviation constraints (59 and 60) under an aid agreement without any commitment bind in the lowest state $n = 1$, i.e. $\check{\rho}_1 > 0$ and $\sigma_1 > 0$, Lemma 10 implies that $\check{c}_1 < \tilde{c}_1$. Furthermore, assume that $\check{d}_2 < \tilde{d}_2$ and $\tilde{\tau}_2 = 0$ in state $n = 2$. The budget constraint (43 and 58) in state $n = 2$ then requires that $\check{c}_2 > \tilde{c}_2$, which may entail that $\check{c}_2 > e_2 > \tilde{c}_2$.

In this case, the recipient's no-deviation constraint (59) under an aid agreement without any commitment in state $n = 2$, which is satisfied with equality by Lemma 6, yields that $\check{\tau}_2 > 0$. While this demonstrates that $\check{\tau}_{n+1} > \tilde{\tau}_{n+1}$ may hold when $\check{\rho}_n > 0$ and $\sigma_n > 0$ for the lowest state $n = 1$, the same logic applies to any higher state $n \in \{2, \dots, N - 1\}$ as well, thereby completing the proof. Q.E.D.